

InChI-Trust OER Administrator Manual

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Using the InChI OER

A. Navigating to the OER

Start by going to InChI-Trust.org and click the drop-down for “RESOURCES” at the top navigation menu. Among the options will be “INCHI EDUCATION OER” which will take the user to the InChI OER.

B. Filtering and Locating Content

The top of the page contains a welcome message and a short description of the InChI OER. Further below, users will find a helpful video tutorial that will walk them through using the OER. Scrolling down just a little more will show the actual OER which will allow the user to look for content. A screenshot is shown below for what this will look like with the default options and no filters applied by the user.

PUBLISHED	TITLE/LINK	CONTENT TYPE
12/17/09	<i>Pub Chem Chemical Structure Sketcher</i>	OER
	<i>CheMagic Virtual Molecular Model Kit</i>	OER
12/03/15	<i>MolView</i>	OER
12/01/15	<i>Using MolView.org to check your structures in organic chemistry</i>	OER
	<i>Hack-a-Mol</i>	OER
10/14/23	<i>InChI Trust Web Demo</i>	OER
	<i>InChI and Registry Numbers</i>	OER
	<i>Unraveling compound taxonomies in untargeted metabolomics through artificial intelligence</i>	OER
12/29/21	<i>A chemical kinetic mechanism for combustion and flame propagation of CH₂F₂/O₂/N₂ mixtures</i>	Non OER
03/22/21	<i>Progress towards "Large Molecule" support with InChI</i>	OER

Current Page= 1

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 13 Last

Content Types

OER Post
 Non OER

InChI Tags

InChI Overview
 Organic
 Safety
 Molecular Editor

Scientific Applications

AI/ML
 InChI Development
 Drug Design
 Drug Discovery

InChI Applications

Stereochemistry
 Tautomers
 Isotopologues
 Large Molecules
 Mixtures (MInChI)
 Nanomaterials

Starting with the Content types, users will see that “OER Post” is selected by default. This means that only the actual OER content is being shown in the results. If the user would like to also search for Non OER content then both checkboxes can be selected. Deselecting “OER Post” will remove those items from the search results.

Next, users can select tags from the taxonomy box below to further refine the results to a particular category. Holding down the CTRL button on the keyboard while selecting tags will allow for multiple tags to be picked. Selecting multiple tags works with the (“and”) function to show only results that contain all of the selected tags.

- **Note – Give the system time to update the results after each change before making additional changes.**

As more filters are applied to the OER search, users will notice that the number of pages for results decrease and only the existing tags will be shown that can meet the criteria of all previously selected tags.

Selecting the title of the content will take the user to a new page dedicated to showing the information for that particular material. Some content will contain long detailed articles whereas some may only contain links or meta data.

Installing the Needed Plugins

A. Install Toolset Types

Log in and head to the administration dashboard. (You must be logged in with an administrator account to install plugins.)

Using the administration dashboard navigation menu on the left, hover over the link for plugins. A secondary menu will appear with sub options. Click on Add New.

There are several ways to add a plugin, however the easiest way is to use the search bar at the top to find the desired plugin. Type "Toolset Types" into the search bar.

You should now have a list of plugins with the first result being the desired plugin. Select Install Now (Image shown has "Update Now" where "Install Now" will be located).

Once you have installed the software a subdirectory will be created under plugins within the site root. You will not see this from the administration dashboard. Once the plugin is installed, you will then need to select the activate button to apply the plugin towards your site.

The screenshot shows the WordPress plugin page for 'Toolset Types – Custom Post Types, Custom Fields and Taxonomies'. On the left is an orange icon of a folder with a document. To the right of the icon, the plugin title is displayed in blue. Below the title is a short description: 'The complete and reliable plugin for managing custom post types, custom taxonomies and custom fields.' and the author 'By OnTheGoSystems'. In the top right corner, there is a purple 'Activate' button with a 'More Details' link underneath it. At the bottom left, there is a star rating of 4.5 out of 5 (271 reviews) and '200,000+ Active Installations'. At the bottom right, it says 'Last Updated: 1 month ago' and 'Compatible with your version of WordPress' with a checkmark.

B. Activate Toolset Types

On the plugins page click the commercial tab to pull up the location where toolset can be activated. You will need to have your activation key ready.

The rest of the steps for activating and installing toolset can be found at the following link.
<https://toolset.com/faq/how-to-install-and-register-toolset/>

The toolset plugins that I have installed as of the current state of this documentation is:

- Toolset Types
- Toolset Views
- Toolset Layouts
- Toolset Forms
- Toolset Access

Adding InChI Post

A. Basic User Form

Users that are logged in and have the correct access permissions will see a link to “ADD INCHI POST” on the top menu bar.

DOWNLOADS OF INCHI SOFTWARE NEWS RESOURCES CONTACT ADD INCHI POST

Once the website presents the form, a basic post can be created that will allow for setting up the title, author(s), uploader(s), content and a few miscellaneous settings such as links and content tags.

Starting at the top, the following fields can be filled out to upload new content.

1. InChI Posts Title

InChI Posts Title

The title to be inserted should be the same as the article or original submission being added to the InChI Resources page.

2. Publication Date

Publication Date

Publication date should match when the article or submission was published on the original submission. If the resource is being added on the InChI-Trust site as original content, then the publication date will be when the final approval is given by one of the editors or administrators.

3. Authors and Uploaders

The screenshot shows a form with two input fields. The first field is labeled "Uploaded By" and the second is labeled "Authors-Contributors-Roles". Below each field is a "+ Add new" button.

The first box is for entering the names of the users responsible for uploading the content to the site. The second field is for entering all original authors and contributors to the resource submission along with the roles involved in its creation.

4. InChI Posts Content

The screenshot shows the "InChI Posts Content" editor. It has a toolbar with buttons for "Add Media", "Fields and Views", "Add PDF", "Toolset Forms", and "Access". There are also "Visual" and "Text" tabs. The main area is a large text input field.

Adding the actual content will take place inside of this field which uses a WYSIWYG (What You See Is What You Get) editor that is very similar to a document text editor. Several features allow for the changing of text styles and formatting. Using the visual tab allows for seeing the text in its final format as it is created. The tab to the right labeled "Text" will allow the user to submit the content through typing html.

If the content being added is original content that the uploader has permission to use, then the content of the resource can be added in its entirety.

Content published elsewhere should simply have a summary or description of the resource put into the content field to give users an overview.

Users also can link to other content within the InChI-Trust site and add media, however this is a little more complex than adding text and may require consulting with the toolset manual at the toolset.com website.

5. Meta Information Boxes

Content Link (Enter the link to the content here if applicable.)

+ Add new

Content Use License

Onsite material must have a license that allows reuse with modification.

+ Add new

DOI

+ Add new

The first box contains several fields for adding additional information about the resource. Multiple submissions can be made for each field.

Upload Content File

+ Add new

Content Images

+ Add new

Content that has permission to be uploaded onto the platform can be uploaded by clicking “Upload or Select File”. This will allow for many different formats to be uploaded. Images from the resource can also be uploaded here if they have permission to do so.

6. Tagging and Indexing Fields

The screenshot shows a form with a light green background. At the top, it is titled "Content Types" and contains two checkboxes: "OER Post" and "Non OER". Below this is a section titled "InChi Tags" which is enclosed in a scrollable box. This box contains several categories, each with a checkbox: "Audience" (with sub-items "Graduate", "Researcher", and "Undergraduate"), "Content type" (with sub-items "Document", "Poster", and "Presentation"), and "Presentation". At the bottom of the form is a green "SUBMIT" button.

The final field is a multi-select style box. At the top the content should either be associated with “OER Post” or “Non OER”. Before selecting which content type to associate with the resource, it may be necessary to discuss this with an editor or administrator to be clear of how these terms are defined.

Maximizing the chance of a user finding appropriate resources through the filter means applying all terms that relate to the article by selecting the appropriate boxes. New terms can be added by those with editor and administrator privileges.

After making all changes, be sure and click submit to send the submission for final publishing approval. The submission will not be visible on the site until it has been approved so users should not continue to keep trying to upload the content.

B. Using the Administrator Form

To access the administrator form, you must be inside of the WordPress administrator dashboard. Once the administrator dashboard has been opened, you should select “Add New” under InChI Posts in the top-left corner.

Once the form is opened, you will have many more options to make a post and configure specific details that is not shown on the regular post form.

Note:

- It is recommended to leave the layout as the Default layout (No sidebars: full width layout).

1. Add InChI Post Title

The title to be inserted should be the same as the article or original submission being added to the InChI Resources page.

2. InChI Posts Content

The image shows a screenshot of a web-based text editor. At the top, there is a text input field labeled "Enter title here". Below this is a toolbar with several buttons: "Add Media", "Add slideshow", "Fields and Views", "Access", "Add Form", and "13". To the right of the toolbar are two tabs: "Visual" (which is active) and "Text". The "Visual" tab contains a rich set of formatting icons including bold, italic, underline, text color, background color, bulleted list, numbered list, link, unlink, and image. Below the toolbar is a large, empty text area for entering content. At the bottom left of the text area, it says "Word count: 0".

Adding the actual content will take place inside of this field which uses a WYSIWYG (What You See Is What You Get) editor that is very similar to a document text editor. Several features allow for the changing of text styles and formatting. Using the visual tab allows for seeing the text in its final format as it is created. The tab to the right labeled “Text” will allow the user to submit the content through typing html.

If the content being added is original content that the uploader has permission to use, then the content of the resource can be added in its entirety.

Content published elsewhere should simply have a summary or description of the resource put into the content field to give users an overview.

Users also can link to other content within the InChI-Trust site and add media, however this is a little more complex than adding text and may require consulting with the toolset manual at the toolset.com website.

3. Skipping Sections

The next 3 sections of the form can be skipped which include the “AIOSEO Settings”, “Slider Options”, and “Layout Options”.

4. InChI Content Fields Group

Content Link – Enter the URL that will point the user to a location where the original submission can be found if the material was published at another location.

Upload Content File – If the material is in a file type such as a slideshow, image or digital format that cannot be put into the WYSIWYG body for the content, this box will allow you to upload the file.

Content Images – Upload any images that will be used in the content body here for storage in the system. Once uploaded, the images needed in the content body can then be displayed through linking them to the image uploads.

Content Use License – Any license that the material holds such as “Creative Commons” can be listed in the box. If the content holds more than one license you can select the “Add New” button

DOI – If the content has a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) you can enter that in this box. Click add if the content has more than one DOI.

Authors-Contributors-Roles – This box is for entering everyone that helped with the creation of the content. Each person should be entered in a separate box. Click “Add New” to add each additional person and their role.

Content Types – This section has two checkboxes. Click “OER Post” if the content can be uploaded in its entirety to the OER and has open access rights. “Non OER” applies to any content published on another platform where the content cannot be reproduced on the InChI OER. In this case only the information about the material will be added to the InChI OER and linked to the original publication source.

Uploaded By – Here you will enter the name of the person that has added the information about the content into the InChI OER. This may not necessarily be the original author of the content.

Publication Date – This date should be for when the content was first published on another platform or for “OER Post” when the content was uploaded to the InChI OER.

5. Discussion

This section can be skipped over leaving the checkboxes unchecked.

6. Author

Select the current user uploading the content. This should already be set to the user that is logged in.

7. Skip the Twitter Sections

The last two sections are not needed for InChI Post.

8. Right Sidebar Sections

The only important tabs on the right sidebar that should be used are the “InChI Tags” and the “Publish” sections.

InChI Tags – Select all tags that represent the content being added.

- New tags can be added by clicking the “Add New InChI Tag”. The image below shows the options that will appear after selecting to add a new tag. Type the name of the tag into the text box and select the drop down below to pick where the tag will be nested among the already existing tags. After the information is added, select the “Add New InChI Tag” button below to add the tag. You can add as many new tags as needed by repeating the steps for each

The image shows a form for adding a new InChI tag. At the top, there is a blue link that says "+ Add New InChI Tag". Below this link is a text input field with a vertical cursor on the left. Underneath the text field is a dropdown menu with the text "— Parent InChI Tag —" and a downward-pointing arrow on the right. At the bottom of the form is a blue button with the text "Add New InChI Tag".

Publish – This section is for setting the view of the content to the public. Click on the button for “Save Draft” to hold the content in the system until it is ready to be published for public viewing. Once the content is finalized, click the “Publish” button to allow the content to be viewed on the OER page. Some of the other options can be used if specific needs for the content are required. There is an option to preview the content in the way that it will be viewed by the public without the content actually being published.

The image shows a 'Publish' settings panel with the following elements:

- Buttons: 'Save Draft' and 'Preview' (top left and right).
- Status: 'Draft' with an 'Edit' link (lock icon).
- Visibility: 'Public' with an 'Edit' link (eye icon).
- Publishing: 'Publish immediately' with an 'Edit' link (calendar icon).
- Checkbox: 'Don't update the modified date'.
- AI SEO Score: '0/100' (gear icon, highlighted in red).
- Bottom Button: 'Publish'.

Editing an InChI Post

A. Basic User Form

Any user that is logged in with the correct access permissions will see an icon towards the top of the post that they are looking at. Clicking this icon will take you to a basic post editing page where basic changes can be made and then updated.

B. Using the Administrator Form

To access the administrator post edit form, you must have the correct access permissions. Within the administrator dashboard of WordPress, click the “InChI Post “ menu option to bring up a list of content.

After you find the post that you would like to edit, hover over the title to bring up the administrative options. Select edit to make adjustments to the post.

Once the changes have been made, click the update button in the box on the right to record the changes. Alternatively, if the content was in draft form, you can choose to send it to published status through this method.

1. Differences from the “Add InChI Form”

The form used by administrators to make changes to an InChI Post will be identical to the form used to create new InChI Post. The only difference is that in the publishing box, the user should select “Don’t update the modified date” box when selecting publish so that it will retain the original creation date from the content was uploaded. The content will still maintain a date for when the draft changes were made in the system.

The image shows a 'Publish' form interface. At the top, the word 'Publish' is displayed in a dark blue font, followed by three small navigation icons (up, down, and left-pointing triangle). Below this, there are two buttons: 'Save Draft' on the left and 'Preview' on the right. The main content area contains several settings, each with an icon and a label: a key icon for 'Status: Draft' with an 'Edit' link; an eye icon for 'Visibility: Public' with an 'Edit' link; a calendar icon for 'Publish immediately' with an 'Edit' link; a checkbox for 'Don't update the modified date' which is currently unchecked; and a gear icon for 'AI/SEO Score' with a red-bordered box containing the value '0/100'. At the bottom right of the form is a large blue 'Publish' button.

- **Note** - This form will allow the administrator to change any area of the content that was available in the original creation form.

Taxonomy

A. Adding/Editing Terms

Terms can be added using the default WordPress interface by simply navigating to the “InChI Tags” link under the administrative dashboard interface.

All of the current terms will be listed on this page, however you may have to navigate through them to find your particular term. You may also add terms and set the Parent InChI Tag through this page.

To edit a term, first hover over the term and more options will appear with an option for edit.

B. Adding/Editing Terms-Basic User Form

The basic user form does not allow for adding or editing terms, however the post may be tagged or untagged using these forms.

Toolset Specific Information

A. Filter Page Framework

Most of the project undertaking that I built revolved around the page used for filtering the InChI Post. You can access this page by clicking the “RESOURCES” option in the top menu or by going to the following link:

<https://www.inchi-trust.org/oer/>

The following illustration outlines how the filter page elements are nested.

B. Editing the Filter Page Framework

Start by clicking in the administration dashboard on the toolset specific dashboard. Once you retrieve the page, there is an option to click on the “InChI Archive Filter Layout” to enter the development mode.

The first page that you will see is the layout editor which should look the same as below.

Everything that is needed to change the settings on the filter page can be found through this editor. The plus sign can be used to add a new row below the current material as well as dragging it above the material. The Toolset documentation has excellent documentation on how to proceed after reaching this point.

Note: If you need to make any edits to the code, be sure and save a backup because very small differences can cause the entire filter to break and become unresponsive.

C. User Forms Framework

Start by clicking in the administration dashboard on the toolset specific dashboard. Once you retrieve the page, there is an option to click on the “Add/Edit InChi Post” to enter the development mode.

Front-end		
Views ?	Views ?	Forms ?
Content Filter Layout	<ul style="list-style-type: none">InChI Content Filter ViewAll Publications <p>How to add Views to layouts</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Add InChI PostEdit InChI Post <p>How to add forms to layouts</p>

Once the page loads you can change several options and add/edit the html to adjust how the form looks or operates. The Toolset documentation has lots of information for how to use the form editor.

A. Where To Make CSS Changes

There are two places where toolset stores the CSS and JavaScript code for making changes.

The first place is on a dedicated page called “Layouts CSS and JS” which can be accessed from the administrator menu as shown below.

When you access this page, there is a tab for both CSS and JavaScript code. This page is mostly for adding any styling or behavior codes that cannot be added using the second method. Any code added here will be applied to any page on the site that calls a class inserted into the editor.

The second place is a better option for adding the code because it only runs on the page in which it was inserted. You can find these editors in places where Toolset gives you an html editor by clicking the dropdown below the box as seen in the following screenshot.

